

WORKFLOW DEMONSTRATION

Example 1

Client Application

Undergraduate Course System

Document

Student Diploma

Step 1 - Create Template

The screenshot displays a REST client interface with the following details:

- Environment:** Blockchain Team, No Environment
- Path:** custom-doc-storage / model / models
- Method:** POST
- URL:** http://localhost/models
- Body (Request):**

```
1 {
2   "description": "Student Diploma",
3   "attributes": "idInternal;hashDoc;courseName;idStudent;status",
4   "modelName": "Diploma",
5   "atttNotNull": "courseName;idStudent;status"
6 }
```
- Status:** 200 OK, Time: 641 ms, Size: 905 B
- Body (Response):**

```
1 {
2   "result": {
3     "returnCode": "success",
4     "modelCode": "fnoanobogkzsdSyui",
5     "message": "Modelo criado com sucesso!"
6   }
7 }
```

Step 2 - Deploy Contract (Polygon Blockchain)

The screenshot displays a REST client interface for a project named "Blockchain Team". The active environment is "No Environment". The current endpoint is "custom-doc-storage / contract / contracts" with a "POST" method. The request body is a JSON object:

```
1 {
2   "blockchain": "3",
3   "modelCode": "fnoanobgkzsd5yui"
4 }
```

The response status is "200 OK" with a time of "7.40 s" and a size of "7.21 KB". The response body is a JSON object:

```
1 {
2   "result": {
3     "returnCode": "success",
4     "contractDeployed": {
5       "idContract": "fnoanobgkzsdnks3",
6       "address": "0x97991F8f4c8B2D0eab44c351732232FC5Ec38dfc",
7       "ABI": [
8         {
9           "constant": true,
10          "inputs": [
11            {
12              "name": "_idDocument",
13              "type": "string"
14            }
15          ],
16          "name": "readDocument",
17          "outputs": [
18            {
19              "name": "",
20              "type": "string[]"
21            }
22          ]
23        }
24      ]
25    }
26  }
27 }
```

Step 3 - Insert Document

The screenshot shows a REST client interface with the following details:

- Environment:** Blockchain Team, No Environment
- Path:** custom-doc-storage / documents / documents
- Method:** POST
- URL:** http://localhost/documents
- Body (Request):**

```
1 {
2   "idContract": "fnoanobogkzsdnks3",
3   "value": ["idInternal001", "hashMedia001", "Software Engineering", "000001", "APPROVED"]
4 }
```
- Status:** 200 OK, Time: 9.74 s, Size: 983 B
- Body (Response - Pretty):**

```
1 {
2   "result": {
3     "returnCode": "success",
4     "blockchain": "3",
5     "idDocument": "fnoanobogkzsdos61",
6     "blockNumber": 25060195,
7     "txId": "0x7fdb83ff4e3c81982757f6d3285b8825fa018410dcd6dd3b798abd901a4108cd"
8   }
9 }
```

Step 4 - Read Document

The screenshot displays a REST client interface for a service named "Blockchain Team". The active endpoint is "POST documents read" with the URL "http://localhost/documents_read". The request body is a JSON object:

```
1 {
2   "idContract": "fnoanobogkzsdnks3",
3   "idDocument": "fnoanobogkzsdos61"
4 }
```

The response status is 200 OK, with a time of 867 ms and a size of 1.09 KB. The response body is a JSON object:

```
1 {
2   "result": {
3     "returnCode": "success",
4     "blockchain": "3",
5     "document": {
6       "idInternal": "idInternal001",
7       "hashDoc": "hashMedia001",
8       "courseName": "Software Engineering",
9       "idStudent": "000001",
10      "status": "APPROVED"
11    },
12    "transactionId": "0x7fdb83ff4e3c81982757fd3285b8825fa018410dc6dd3b798abd901a4108cd",
13    "timestamp": "2022-02-18T12:18:33.000Z"
14  }
15 }
```

Example 2

Client Application

System for Generating a Copyright Certificate for Artworks

Document

ArtWork Certificate

Step 1 - Create Template

The screenshot displays a REST client interface for a project named "Blockchain Team". The active tab is "POST models" with the URL "http://localhost/models". The request body is a JSON object:

```
1 {
2   "description": "Artwork Certificate in General",
3   "attributes": "idInternal;hashDoc;idArtwork;idAuthor;description;artworkType",
4   "modelName": "Artwork Certificate",
5   "attrNotNull": "idArtwork;idAuthor;description;artworkType"
6 }
```

The response status is "200 OK" with a time of 724 ms and a size of 905 B. The response body is a JSON object:

```
1 {
2   "result": {
3     "returnCode": "success",
4     "modelCode": "fnoanobgkzse8ux1",
5     "message": "Modelo criado com sucesso!"
6   }
7 }
```

Step 2 - Deploy Contract (Ethereum Blockchain)

The screenshot displays a REST client interface for a project named "Blockchain Team". The active tab is "POST contracts" with the endpoint "http://localhost/contracts". The request body is a JSON object:

```
1 {
2   "blockchain": "0",
3   "modelCode": "fnoanobogkzse8ux1"
4 }
```

The response is shown in the "Body" section, formatted as JSON:

```
1 {
2   "result": {
3     "returnCode": "success",
4     "contractDeployed": {
5       "idContract": "fnoanobogkzsearch",
6       "address": "0xaF4c91Bb8b5F6f91EED1009a42844F3BBeDDdeb5",
7       "ABI": [
8         {
9           "constant": true,
10          "inputs": [
11            {
12              "name": "_idDocument",
13              "type": "string"
14            }
15          ],
16          "name": "readDocument",
17          "outputs": [
18            {
19              "name": "",
20              "type": "string[]"
21            }
22          ]
23        }
24      ]
25    }
26  }
27 }
```

The status bar indicates a successful response: Status: 200 OK, Time: 58.69 s, Size: 7.21 KB.

Step 3 - Insert Document

The screenshot shows a REST client interface for a project named "Blockchain Team". The active environment is "No Environment". The selected collection is "custom-doc-storage / documents / documents". The request is a POST to "http://localhost/documents".

Request Body (JSON):

```
1 {
2   "idContract": "fnoanobogkzsearch",
3   "value": ["idInternal002", "698dc19d489c4e4db73e28a713eab07b", "000001", "000002", "A digital drawing of the Eiffel Tower landscape.", "Digital Drawing"]
4 }
```

Response Body (JSON):

```
1 {
2   "result": {
3     "returnCode": "success",
4     "blockchain": "0",
5     "idDocument": "fnoanobogkzsegfkt",
6     "blockNumber": 10189492,
7     "txId": "0xd9ce8c45813668638dbc3b338af5e376c940034543f6df597476b055b480843d"
8   }
9 }
```

The response status is 200 OK, with a time of 19.82 s and a size of 983 B.

Step 4 - Read Document

The screenshot shows a REST client interface with the following details:

- Environment:** Blockchain Team, No Environment
- Path:** custom-doc-storage / documents / documents read
- Method:** POST
- URL:** http://localhost/documents_read
- Body (Request):**

```
1 {
2   "idContract": "fnoanobogkzsearch",
3   "idDocument": "fnoanobogkzsegfkt"
4 }
```
- Status:** 200 OK, Time: 937 ms, Size: 1.17 KB
- Body (Response):**

```
1 {
2   "result": {
3     "returnCode": "success",
4     "blockchain": "0",
5     "document": {
6       "idInternal": "idInternal002",
7       "hashDoc": "698dc19d489c4e4db73e28a713eab07b",
8       "idArtwork": "000001",
9       "idAuthor": "000002",
10      "description": "A digital drawing of the Eiffel Tower landscape.",
11      "artworkType": "Digital Drawing"
12    },
13    "transactionId": "0xd9ce8c45813668638dbc3b338af5e376c940034543f6df597476b055b480843d",
14    "timestamp": "2022-02-18T12:40:13.000Z"
15  }
16 }
```